

CHALLENGE

Use of antimicrobials leads to the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance, which is a serious threat to the health of people and animals. However a further limitation of the use of antimicrobials in animals might put the health and welfare of the animals at risk, hence there is the urgent need to find alternatives for the treatment or prevention of respiratory and digestive tract infections in livestock.

SOLUTION

AVANT is a multi-actor inter-sectorial project aimed at developing alternatives to antimicrobials for the management of bacterial infections in pigs, especially diarrhoea during the weaning period, as the major indication for antimicrobial use in livestock in Europe. During pre-clinical studies efficacy, toxicity and mode of action of these interventions are tested and their dosage and formulation optimised. The results and a survey of veterinarian-, farmer- and consumer perception of antimicrobial alternatives will be used together with legal and economic considerations to select three interventions for large-scale farm trials, assessing clinical efficacy and impact on antimicrobial use.

MAIN OBJECTIVES

AVANT aims to produce a complementary set of alternatives to treat or prevent post-weaning diarrhoea and respiratory infections:

- Gut-stabilising interventions based on a synbiotic (pre- and probiotic) product and faecal microbiota transplantation
- Novel veterinary medicinal products containing bacteriophages and polymers for targeted treatment of enterotoxigenic *E. coli* infections
- Development of injectable and oral immunostimulants
- Alternative feeding strategies targeting sows and piglets

All steps are supported by regulatory advice for quick market entry post-project. Generated and existing data on antimicrobial use, pig demographics and projected consumption of pork will be used in mathematical modelling to estimate the reduction in antimicrobial use that could be achieved by 2030 if the AVANT alternatives were widely adopted in pig production.

CONSORTIUM

SMEs/Associations

Industry

Academia

FACT BOX

EU Contribution: € 6 Million
Overall budget: € 6.6 Million
Start date: 01/01/2020
End date: 31/12/2024

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